

Residue properties

3810343

a. Absolute deviation from mean Chi-1 value (excl. Pro)

b. Absolute deviation from mean of omega torsion

c. C-alpha chirality: abs. deviation of zeta torsion

Highlighted residues are those that deviate by more than 2.0 st. devs. from ideal

d. Secondary structure & estimated accessibility

e. Sequence & Ramachandran regions

f. Max. deviation (see listing)

g. G-factors

c = cis-peptide

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Key:- Helix Beta strand Random coil Accessibility shading: Buried Accessible

e. Sequence & Ramachandran regions Most favoured Allowed Generous Disallowed

f. Max. deviation (see listing)

g. G-factors

	Ave
Phi-psi	-0.56
Chi1-chi2	0.16
Chi1 only	0.09
Chi3 & chi4	0.46
Omega	-0.25
Dihedrals	-0.13
MC bonds	-0.46
MC angles	-0.74
Mainchain	-0.62
Overall	-0.30